

In-Context Interference In Chat-Based Large Language Models

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Abstract. Large Language Models (LLMs) have transformed society, but modifying their internal knowledge remains challenging. Here, we focus on interference in in-context learning, examining how new knowledge affects performance in self-aware robots. We propose an evaluation benchmark based on the bAbI dataset to assess the robot’s ability to manage interference, maintain stability, ensure flexible information routing, and facilitate task performance. Addressing these challenges is crucial for improving LLMs’ effectiveness in developing self-aware robots.

1 Introduction

Chat-based applications based on LLMs have gained attention for their versatile capabilities across various tasks, including medical question answering and patient-trial matching in the medical field [18]. In robotics, LLMs are increasingly integrated into autonomous industrial robotics and task planning, playing a crucial role in decision-making, task execution, and autonomous design within manufacturing contexts [7, 16].

While LLMs excel at understanding and engaging in conversations, modifying their internal knowledge is still challenging. Most approaches rely on adding new information via prompt engineering due to the inability to modify private models’ weight (e.g. ChatGPT). This approach is known as In-context learning, and this paper extends the discussion to a comprehensive understanding of their limitations and strengths. We focus on studying the model’s behavior by presenting a new benchmark based on the bAbI dataset, shedding light on potential limitations and enhancing overall performance. The problems presented in this work will facilitate the development of more robust and efficient language models, especially for a reliable interaction between users and self-aware robots, particularly in chat-based applications.

Our main contributions can be summarized as follows: (1) Proposing a benchmark to assess the accumulation and retention of information in LLMs, addressing their capabilities and limitations in in-context learning. (2) This benchmark reveals evidence of interference within the same chat session, impacting performance as new information is added, which is critical when relying on a continual stream of information. (3) We provide insights into the current ability of these models to learn, retain, and reason on in-context scenarios.

2 Related Works

In-Context Learning Recent research highlights the significance of in-context learning in chat-based LLMs [8]. Meta-in-context learning is explored for recursive improvement across various tasks through meta-learning [4]. Innovative methods like LAMOC are used for knowledge-based visual question answering [6]. McL-KBQA framework utilizes in-context learning for knowledge base question answering in low-resource settings [13]. Long-term reasoning for chat-based LLMs is challenging [15] and TempReason dataset is used to enhance LLMs’ temporal reasoning capability [14].

Continual Learning in LLMs Most methods in Continual Learning (CL) that works with LLMs, focus on training soft prompts [12] or adapters [10], modifying model weights for specific tasks. In contrast, our approach examines the influence CL in a in-context approach.

LLMs In Self-Aware Robots LLMs can enhance autonomous robots by providing natural language understanding, reasoning, and generation. Researchers have proposed a unified system where a large language model can summarize and answer questions about a robot’s activities [5]. Researchers have also introduced CODEBOTLER [9], an open-source tool for programming robots through natural language. A benchmark called ROBOEVAL can assess LLMs in generating accurate sequences of robot actions and provide insights into common pitfalls and failures.

3 In-Session evaluation

Typically, users engage with chat-based LLMs in closed sessions, treating the model as a black-box. Interaction is limited to prompts via the chat interface, expecting flawless recall of prior exchanges. We propose testing knowledge retrieval by gradually increasing stored information. Starting from knowledge s_0 , we ask the LLM questions q_0 associated with input s_0 , obtaining performance per_0 . At time step i , we will add input s_i to the context and ask all questions $q_{\leq i}$, meaning questions from input s_0 to s_i , to obtain performance per_i . If the model does not suffer from interference and flawlessly recalls prior knowledge, one should expect that performance should stay the same as we add new knowledge.

3.1 Benchmark

To evaluate knowledge retrieval and study the interference, we propose a benchmark based on a subset of the bAbI dataset [17]. This sequence of stories provided a stream of knowledge that the model must remember to answer the questions without depending on prior information correctly. Here, we evaluate only the retention capacity of the information delivered in the context.

We simplified the dataset by renaming entities and retained only the last two statements, along with a question about the final entity. This approach helped us evaluate the model’s context retention and question-answering accuracy. One limitation lies in the token limit, considering both computational capacity and the context size for optimal model performance. We selected 50 stories as a hyper-parameter, but this can be adjusted as the token limit of LLMs increases.

4 Experiments

We use the Vicuna model [3] within the LangChain [2] framework to evaluate the previous scenario. Due to computational limitations, we set the maximum number of tokens to 2048. Because the answer we are looking at is only one word long, to reduce the probability of longer answers, we empirically found that a temperature of 0.7 provides the best performance overall. Following previous work of in-context learning, we teach the model with prompt engineering.

4.1 One Context-One Story

As a baseline, we verify the model’s ability to correctly answer questions in a one-story-per-context scenario, removing possible interference within the context. The accuracy when using the whole story is 58%, as observed in our experiments. This low accuracy and the high number of tokens per story encourage us to propose the simplified version of the known dataset mentioned in the previous section. When testing the performance of the simplified version, the model obtained a 100%, probing that the complexity of the original dataset could interfere with the conclusions drawn.

4.2 Incremental stories

Typically, users assume that LLMs accumulate information without interference with the previous context. We hypothesise that introducing new information can lead to interference, which can cause a decrease in performance. Recognizing this limitation allows us to study and propose methods to minimize training and token limitations.

As shown in Figure 1a, as we add new knowledge to the prompts, the performance of the model decreases from 100% with only one story to around 75% when we have 8 in the same context. A similar effect appears when using the original stories, where the model shows a decrease in performance.

Due to the limitations of LLMs, we cannot significantly increase the number of stories since the number of tokens in the model is truncated during training. Some studies have shown that it is possible to increase the number of tokens [1] with little performance loss; however, this increases the computational cost. We also observed in our experiments that as we increase the size of the prompt (# of stories and length), the cost of delivering a response increases.

4.3 Summarizing

The interference between old and new information is not something new. The problem known as Catastrophic Forgetting (CF) [11] is precisely caused by the continual weight modification when training a Deep Learning model. However, it is a different process than the one presented here, where the model’s weights are not modified. In this case, the interference is at the information level, and the model is unable to identify the relevant parts of all the information delivered correctly.

Like the CF problem, we need to minimize interference in the model’s accumulated context. One approach is using built-in summarizing tools to reduce

Fig. 1: Figure (a) shows the accuracy obtained when adding new knowledge to the context using short and full stories. Figure (b) shows the accuracy when removing or summarizing short stories stored in the context.

stored tokens while retaining crucial knowledge in the buffer. This allows the model to compress information, diminishing interference with unnecessary details and enhancing performance. However, performance may decline during information summarization, as illustrated in the figure 1b.

One theory of the above is that the model may interfere with the responses it has delivered (which are part of the context). For this reason, instead of summarizing the previous information, we deleted old stories and only kept 6 in the context. By removing old stories, we remove the option for the model to change its response (for better or worse), but more importantly, we are reducing the amount of tokens that cause interference. As shown in Figure 1b, the model is able to preserve most of the performance even with a high number of stories.

5 Conclusion

This paper introduces a novel benchmark to assess how chat-based LLMs are impacted by interference in in-context learning. We proposed a bAbI dataset-based benchmark to evaluate the models’ ability to accumulate information in the context. Our findings reveal that introducing new information causes interference, negatively affecting model performance in user-uncontrolled scenarios. While this study addresses the limitations of in-context learning, it lays the groundwork for further exploration, including issues like interference between context-based and pre-trained knowledge in models.

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